

Speed behaviours, speed limit compliance of commercial vehicles and road characteristics in Leeds, UK

Long Chen^{*1}, Ed Manley^{†1}

¹Consumer Data Research Centre; Mobility Science Lab; School of Geography;
University of Leeds, Leeds LS2 9JT, UK

GISRUK 2024

Summary

Speed behaviours such as speed limit compliance/adherence, acceleration, and deceleration are important facets in urban mobility, connected with transport planning, road safety, and energy issues. This study used detailed trajectories of commercial vehicles to investigate speed behaviours at road segment level in Leeds. Results show distinctive speed limit adherence, acceleration, and deceleration characteristics in road hierarchy and urban areas, highlighting the neglected speed behaviours in urban mobility.

KEYWORDS: Speed behaviour; Speed limit compliance; Acceleration; Deceleration;
Urban mobility

1. Introduction

Speed behaviours of vehicles are important facets in transport planning, road safety, urban livability, and environment sustainability. Speed behaviours of vehicles and drivers pertaining to speeding, acceleration and deceleration, and speed limit compliance/adherence are essential characteristics to understand, which are primarily associated with road design characteristics and the urban environment. Yet, limited studies have explored these speed behaviours.

Excessive driving speed is a threat for road safety as it has been found to increase both the frequency and severity of road traffic accidents (Aarts & van Schagen, 2006). Speed limit compliance/adherence is of paramount importance in vehicle speed behaviours. Prior studies have established the effects of posted speed limits on traffic flow and congestion (Heydecker & Addison, 2011), and speed limit compliance on road capacity (Kumar et al., 2020). Acceleration and deceleration behaviours are also important for road infrastructure design. The curb extension at zebra crossing is an effective measure to induce appropriate speed and reduce deceleration behaviours (Bella & Silvestri, 2015). Road bump/humps have been widely utilized in speed control design (Antić et al., 2013).

Despite the importance of vehicle speed, it remains challenge to collect speed information in a large scale. Traditional studies obtaining speed behaviours are often conducted by questionnaire survey (Elliott et al., 2003), limited sites observation (Eboli et al., 2017; Montella et al., 2015), and simulated driving environment (Pawar et al., 2023). In light of the emerging of real-time vehicle mobility data, large scale vehicle trajectories with detailed speed characteristics are available. Investigation on speed behaviours at finer spatial-temporal granularity is urgent in mobility studies and related consequences.

2. Data

This study used a large sampling of commercial vehicle journeys supplied by Compass IoT, collected in October 2023 for one month. Each record, corresponding to one vehicle journey, includes vectors including coordinates, snapped timestamp, and speed. This study used data in Leeds city, and reorganized the vectors of journeys into snapped points. The dataset in Leeds contains 3,008,530 individual point records within 44,321 unique journeys. It is one of the first times such detailed vehicle trajectories has been made available with speed information.

* geolche@leeds.ac.uk

† e.j.manley@leeds.ac.uk

Figure 1: Compass commercial vehicle record points in Leeds

3. Method

Speed acceleration (or deceleration) at each point is calculated using timestamp and speed fields. The equation is as follows:

$$Acc = \frac{S_2 - S_1}{t_2 - t_1}$$

Then, the spatiotemporal characteristics of speed, acceleration, and deceleration behaviours are analyzed within the snapped points in Leeds. Acceleration and deceleration points are extracted by positive and negative values of accelerated speed. Acceleration partition is divided into low, medium, high, and extreme accelerations by quartiles, as well as deceleration partition, respectively. Then, heatmap for temporal variation of 24-hour percent of point counts in speed, acceleration, and deceleration quartiles are explored.

In addition, point records are aligned with road segments using geospatial join points to nearest lines. Assessment of speed limit adherence is conducted by calculating the percent of points with speed below the speed limit at road segment. Moreover, spatial visualization of percent of points at road segment level by speed, acceleration, and deceleration quartiles are implemented. Moreover,

4. Results

Heatmaps in Figure 2a, 2b, and 2c illustrate temporal variation of the hourly percent of point counts for speed, acceleration, and deceleration quartiles, respectively. The distributions of speeds (Fig 2a) show a broadly expected pattern - the lowest speeds (Q1) are shown during morning and evening peak periods, and the fastest speeds (Q4) found during the nighttime. The acceleration, and deceleration events (Fig 2b, 2c) suggest a more intriguing finding – whereby rapid acceleration and deceleration events are more common during the daytime than at night.

Figure 2c: Temporal variation of speed deceleration

Figure 3 demonstrates average speed at each road. Road-level average speed distinguished that road segments with lower average speed are located in and around city center, while segments with higher speed are observed along the major motorways.

Figure 3: Average speed at road segments

Figure 3 a-d show percent of point counts in different speed quartiles at segment scale. Very low (Q1), and low (Q2) speeds tend to be clustered at areas with high density of road networks, and dense urban areas. However, high (Q3), and very high (Q4) speeds tend to be accommodated in highways and major roads.

Fig 3 a-d: Percent of counts for speed quartiles (Q1-Q4)

Speed limit adherence by speed limit classes, and road hierarchy are investigated in Leeds (Table 1). Results show that speed limit at 5, 10, 15, 20 mph have the lowest adherence rate. Road hierarchies including minor road, local road, secondary access road have the lowest adherence rate. Figure 4 shows the speed limit adherence rate at road segment level in Leeds, demonstrating that roads with lower adherence rate are distributed at suburban residential areas.

Table 1: Speed limit adherence by speed limit classes, and road hierarchy

Speed limit class	Adherence rate	Road class	Adherence rate
5 mph	24.5%	A Road	92.6%
10 mph	66.4%	A Road Primary	94.7%
15 mph	71.6%	B Road	91.7%
20 mph	78.3%	Local Access Road	96.2%
30 mph	92.0%	Local Road	90.3%
40 mph	94.6%	Minor Road	85.2%
50 mph	96.0%	Motorway	94.3%
60 mph	99.7%	Restricted Local Access Road	96.7%
70 mph	98.6%	Restricted Secondary Access Road	92.1%
		Secondary Access Road	88.9%

Figure 4: Speed limit adherence rate at road segments

Figure 5 illustrates average acceleration and deceleration at road segment level. The mean value derived from points in segment indicate overall acceleration and deceleration patterns. Results show that extreme acceleration and deceleration road segments are located at main roads, particularly around junctions, and suburban residential segments. There are no obvious clusters grids of deceleration and acceleration.

Figure 5 a-b: Average speed acceleration, and deceleration at road segments

Figure 6 a-d, and figure 7 a-d showcase percent of point counts at road segment scale pertaining to low, medium, high, and extreme acceleration, and deceleration behaviours, respectively. Roads with high percent of extreme acceleration behaviours are clustered around junctions of road networks, while the extreme deceleration behaviours seem to be located in main roads and junctions, particularly in suburban residential areas.

Figure 6 a-d: Percent of counts in acceleration quartiles

Figure 7 a-d: Percent of points in deceleration quartiles

5. Conclusion

The study highlighted the interesting and distinctive characteristics of speed, acceleration, and

deceleration behaviours in Leeds. The variation of commercial vehicle's speed behaviours, speed limit compliance, and road characteristics opens up new opportunities for considering urban mobility, which should be investigated to understand the latent mechanisms and factors influencing these behaviours. Research objectives can be formulated including road speed adherence, traffic safety, urban road infrastructure design, and environmental issues relating with speed behaviours.

Reference

- Aarts, L., & van Schagen, I. (2006). Driving speed and the risk of road crashes: A review. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 38(2), 215–224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2005.07.004>
- Antić, B., Pešić, D., Vujanić, M., & Lipovac, K. (2013). The influence of speed bumps heights to the decrease of the vehicle speed – Belgrade experience. *Safety Science*, 57, 303–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2013.03.008>
- Bella, F., & Silvestri, M. (2015). Effects of safety measures on driver's speed behavior at pedestrian crossings. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 83, 111–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2015.07.016>
- Eboli, L., Guido, G., Mazzulla, G., Pungillo, G., & Pungillo, R. (2017). Investigating Car Users' Driving Behaviour through Speed Analysis. *Promet - Traffic&Transportation*, 29(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.7307/ptt.v29i2.2117>
- Elliott, M. A., Armitage, C. J., & Baughan, C. J. (2003). Drivers' compliance with speed limits: An application of the theory of planned behavior. *The Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 964–972. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.88.5.964>
- Heydecker, B. G., & Addison, J. D. (2011). Analysis and modelling of traffic flow under variable speed limits. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 19(2), 206–217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2010.05.008>
- Kumar, P., Bains, M. S., Bharadwaj, N., Arkatkar, S., & Joshi, G. (2020). Impact assessment of driver speed limit compliance behavior on macroscopic traffic characteristics under heterogeneous traffic environment. *Transportation Letters*, 12(1), 54–65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19427867.2018.1512200>
- Montella, A., Galante, F., Mauriello, F., & Aria, M. (2015). Continuous Speed Profiles to Investigate Drivers' Behavior on Two-Lane Rural Highways. *Transportation Research Record*, 2521(1), 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.3141/2521-01>
- Pawar, N. M., Velaga, N. R., & Mishra, S. (2023). Impact assessment of professional drivers' speed compliance and speed adaptation with posted speed limits in different driving environments and driving conditions. *Transportation Letters*, 0(0), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19427867.2023.2252222>

Biographies

Long Chen, is a research fellow at Consumer Data Research Centre; Mobility Science Lab, School of Geography, University of Leeds. His research interests include geography, urban analytics, urban big data, and mobility.

Ed Manley is a Professor of Urban Analytics in the School of Geography, and member of the Centre for Spatial Analysis and Policy (CSAP) research cluster. He is affiliated with the Leeds Institute for Data Analytics (LIDA), he is a Turing Fellow at the Alan Turing Institute, and Honorary Professor at University College London (UCL). Ed's research deepens our understanding of human mobility in cities, using new forms of data and computational methods to capture how spatial behaviours shape urban activity and dynamics.